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Work Package 5

Integrated personal exposome and metabolomics profile

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the integrated personal exposome and metabolomics profile pilot analyses, part of the concept of exposome monitoring using wearables devices with systematic longitudinal sampling. In the context of the HEAP project, we have devised bioinformatic pipelines tailored to thoroughly analyze the longitudinal exposome and metabolome of participants. The wearables cohort within HEAP comprises 100 healthy pregnant and non-pregnant women, monitored for at least four months through systematic longitudinal sampling using wearables devices (cohort details available in WP5 D5.1 deliverable titled 'Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device') and using analyses methods described in D5.3.

Our meticulous recruitment and monitoring processes form the foundation for this wearable cohort, facilitating the joint longitudinal assessment of individual external exposome, internal metabolome, and their interactions. To describe different components of biotic exposure using wearables, we have implemented two specific pipelines. The Universal Fragment Classification (UFC) pipeline is a comprehensive exposome analysis tool for wearable metagenomes, exhibiting accuracy and reproducibility with a minimum cell input. The CSC-UPAS pipeline focuses on specific species-level detection and phylogenetic variation analyses of abundant microbes, utilizing Metagenome Assembled Genomes (MAGs) and a curated reference database for precise inference of phylogenetic variation in detected species. Currently we are analysing the pilot data of 24 individuals out of the 100 recruited participants with a two month follow up. The full cohort of 100 individuals biotic and abiotic data will be curated in spring 2024 and analysed for a publication during 2024.

Eventually the correlation of external and internal exposure (i.e., exposome) from wearables and urine samples metabolome will offer a holistic perspective on the health status of wearable cohort participants. In summary, these comprehensive analyses of environmental abiotic and biotic exposure, coupled with the internal metabolome, will contribute to a deeper understanding of the exposome and its implications for human health.

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2 Introduction

Previously we conducted a comprehensive and longitudinal analysis of a participant's multi-omics profile, encompassing the exposome, metabolome, proteome, gut microbiome, cytokines, and blood tests (Jiang et al. 2018). The study identified nearly 9,000 statistically significant correlations among nearly 1,700 exposures and health-related features. Positive correlations were more prevalent than negative ones, with the biological exposome and metabolome displaying the most dispersion and correlation. Notably, biological exposures and the metabolome exhibited the most significant correlations within the exposome and internal multi-omics, respectively. Specifically, we found 4624 statistically significant correlations between the exposome and blood metabolome, with salicylic acid, dinoseb, and dibromoethane being the top three environmental chemicals positively correlated with cellular metabolites from blood. Pathway analysis revealed associations with liver and kidney functions, with some pathways correlated with both biological and chemical exposomes.

This groundbreaking work represents the first exploration of correlations between the external exposome and the internal multi-omics of the same individual (Fig 1). The study highlights the potential of systematic monitoring through wearables devices and inter-omics analyses for assessing an individual's personal environmental health. The correlations between the exposome and metabolome were built using Spearman's correlation, and significant metabolites were employed to construct a correlation network and investigate associated pathways. The KEGGs database facilitated pathway enrichment analysis, and dysregulated modules were identified based on metabolic networks using maximum likelihood estimation.

Our exposome approach demonstrates the feasibility of identifying high-degree components crucial in external-internal exposome interactions in humans. The preliminary results generate numerous testable hypotheses for further investigations into the mechanisms underlying exposome impacts on health. The biotic exposome pipelines will be employed in HEAP to analyze the external exposome alongside the internal metabolome. One of our primary objectives is to explore biotic exposures comprehensively, employing the metagenome pipelines for a wide biological spectrum and for deep microorganism resolution to understand the potential role of biotic exposure in human health.

Figure 1. Personal exposome monitoring used wearable Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler (UPAS).

3 Pilot Data Analyses

The pilot data of the cohort entitled '*Monitoring exposures during pregnancy with a wearable device*' and described in detail in WP5 D5.1. encompasses bi-weekly sampling of the wearable Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler (UPAS) device filters (Fig 1). This pilot consists of 27 women followed for 8 weeks with bi-weekly UPAS filter sampling (Fig. 2)

Figure 1. Bi-weekly sampling of the wearable UPAS device filters in parallel with blood/urine sampling.

3.1 Biotic exposome analysis

Our metagenome assembly pipeline describe in D5.3 have been successfully employed for the systematic screening and designed for wearables metagenome analyses, featuring an automated process of splitting input sequence data for parallel database searching and output parsing. These pipelines have been refined for a comprehensive detection purpose, now capable of identifying bacterial, viral, fungal, archaeal, and protozoan species along with their species-level phylogenetic variation. They incorporate an integrated automatic evaluation to check the completeness of results, with a resume option in case of interruptions during prior searching steps. Given the time and computational intensity of searching hundreds or thousands of metagenome contigs through a massive database, careful optimizations are essential to ensure reasonable running times for each sample.

The pipelines initiate with quality control, involving duplication removal and a quality check of sequencing reads. Human reads are then eliminated through mapping to the human reference genome. The use of the megahit algorithm facilitates de novo assembly of reads into contigs, enhancing confidence in subsequent taxonomic classification. Ultimately, high-quality contigs are employed to query our custom-made database for taxonomic mapping, utilizing the Lowest Common Ancestor (LCA) method.

Results of the pilot data

Biological exposome: Nucleic acids were extracted from 27 individuals monitored with the UPAS and sampled with filters for one month bi-weekly, collected during the pilot cohort. Samples were linearly amplified and then made into libraries for sequencing. Libraries were sequenced using novel Ultima sequencing platform. The Ultima sequencing platform enables longer sequencing reads and fast runs with high accuracy (Almogly et al. 2022).

For the pilot sample set, a fast Kraken2 (Woods et al. 2015) based pipeline is used to generate an overview of the dataset. Total of 8349 species were identified from the pilot samples, covering all domains of life. The most abundant kingdoms across all samples are Eukaryota and Metazoa (Figure 2 and 3). Further analysis will be done to assess the effect of time/season in greater detail. At the species

level, the most abundant species are *Micrococcus luteus*, *Moraxella osloensis*, and *Panicum hallii*. Pathogens and opportunistic pathogens, such as *E.coli*, *C.acnes*, *S.aureus* are present in the samples as well.

Figure 2. Kingdom composition of pilot samples

Figure 3. PCA plot of samples on the kingdom level. Eukaryota and Metazoa contribute most to the difference between samples.

Figure 5. Heatmap of the top 25 chemicals with difference between pregnant and non-pregnant women.

4 Summary

The exposome encompasses all exposures throughout an individual's lifetime, exerting a significant influence on personal health. Our research, as well as that of others, indicates a diverse range of abiotic and biotic environmental exposures in our daily lives, far beyond what was previously quantified and understood. Our extensive analysis pipeline and custom database have revealed notable locational and seasonal patterns in the biological and chemical profiles of individuals, demonstrating dynamic changes in samples collected from the same person. Understanding the species-level phylogenetic variation of microorganisms is crucial, as pathogenic potential often varies at the strain level. Our pipelines systematically assess the composition and phylogenetic variation of abundant microbial species derived from the environmental exposome obtained through wearables.

From an individual's genome, microbiome, exposome, and their intricate interactions, human health can be estimated. Traditional methods typically focus on singular stressors, overlooking the intricate nature of the human exposome. We have previously introduced a network approach that integrates the external exposome and internal environment to explore how external stressors impact internal omics and correlate with human health. Our method is groundbreaking in systematically linking individuals' external environmental exposures with internal processes at the omics level. Employing this comprehensive approach to analyze the individual's exposome and metabolome will ultimately offer unparalleled insights into the role of the exposome in human health.

5 References

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